

Effect of Substrate Temperature on RF Sputtered NiO thin films

Saheer Cheemadan, M.C. Santhosh Kumar*

Optoelectronic Materials and Devices Lab, Department of Physics, National Institute of
Technology, Tiruchirappalli- 620 015, India

*Author for correspondence: santhoshmc@nitt.edu

Abstract:

Nickel oxide (NiO) thin films are deposited by RF sputtering process and the physical properties are investigated for various substrate temperatures. The structural, optical and electrical properties of NiO thin films under varying substrate temperatures are reported in this work. The variation of the crystallographic orientation and microstructure of the NiO thin films with increase in substrate temperature are studied using XRD. It was observed that NiO thin films deposited at 350 °C shows relatively good crystalline characteristics with a preferential orientation along (111) plane. SEM and AFM investigations unveil that the microstructure of the thin films improves at higher substrate temperatures. Increase in transmittance is observed for NiO thin films upon increasing the substrate temperature. It is revealed that films prepared at substrate temperature of 350 °C, the NiO films showed higher electrical conductivity which can be utilized for a range of applications as transparent conducting oxides (TCO's) with stable p-type characteristics.

Keywords: Nickel Oxide; RF sputtering; p-type semiconductor